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Work-Related Stress and Teaching Performance of the Elementary School Teachers in Sirawai District, Schools Division of Zamboanga Del Norte: Basis for an Intervention Program

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ABSTRACT: This study aimed to determine the work-related stress and teaching performance of elementary school teachers in Sirawai District, Schools Division of Zamboanga del Norte, during the School Year 2025–2026. A descriptive-correlational research design was employed, involving 146 teachers selected through total enumeration sampling. Data were gathered using a structured questionnaire that measured work-related stress across nine dimensions, while teaching performance was based on the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF). The statistical tools used were weighted mean, standard deviation, and Spearman rank-order correlation at the 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that work-related stress was generally high, with the highest levels observed in resources, classroom management, and time management. Other domains, including lack of support, work-life balance, emotional demands, and role ambiguity, were also rated as very stressful, while workload and assessment and evaluation were rated as moderately stressful. Teaching performance was generally rated Very Satisfactory. Overall work-related stress showed no significant relationship with teaching performance. However, work-life balance stress showed a weak but significant positive relationship with teaching performance. Based on these findings, it is recommended that the Schools Division of Zamboanga del Norte and district officials prioritize the equitable distribution of instructional resources and provide targeted training in classroom management. School heads should also institutionalize Project GABAY to establish a formal support system that addresses role ambiguity and emotional demands.

KEYWORDS: work-related stress, teaching performance, elementary teachers, IPCRF, intervention program

INTRODUCTION

Teaching is regarded as one of the most challenging professions worldwide because it involves emotional demands, workload pressure, and accountability requirements (Asaloei et al., 2020). Teachers' responsibilities extend beyond classroom instruction, as they also manage learners' behavior, provide learner support, prepare assessments, and accomplish various school-related tasks. Due to these multiple responsibilities, teachers commonly experience work-related stress. Work-related stress occurs when the demands of the job exceed an individual's capacity, ability, or available resources to cope effectively (Sarabia & Collantes, 2020). In the field of education, stress is not merely a short-term experience; rather, it may develop into a persistent condition characterized by emotional exhaustion and a sense of being overwhelmed (Brindha.K & Muthukumar, 2026). Reports from international organizations such as the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) indicate that teachers across the world are facing increasing workload demands, particularly in relation to administrative responsibilities and accountability measures.

In the Philippine setting, teacher stress is commonly associated with heavy workloads, strict deadlines, and insufficient administrative support. Elementary school teachers are particularly affected because they are expected to perform not only instructional duties but also documentation, report preparation, and other school-related assignments (Sarabia & Collantes, 2020). These conditions create continuous pressure that may result in burnout, anxiety, and health-related concerns such as hypertension (Agyapong et al., 2022). When stress remains unmanaged for an extended period, it can weaken teachers' engagement, motivation, and effectiveness in performing their professional duties.

Teaching performance is essential in promoting quality instruction and improving learner achievement. In the Philippine public school system, teacher performance is guided by the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) and assessed through the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) under the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS). This evaluation tool measures teachers' performance in areas such as content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, learner diversity, curriculum planning, assessment and reporting, community linkages, and professional growth (Maloloy-on & Arnado, 2023).

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Although the system promotes accountability and professional improvement, teachers are also required to carry out additional duties such as coordination work, documentation, data management, committee assignments, and compliance reports (Oriel & Estrellan, 2025). These added responsibilities make teachers' workload more complex and may reduce the time available for lesson preparation, instructional enhancement, and personal rest. As these demands increase, sustaining high teaching performance becomes a major challenge for many teachers. Teaching performance does not depend solely on teachers' knowledge, skills, and competencies. It is also shaped by factors such as the school environment, administrative support, availability of instructional resources, and professional relationships within the workplace (Bacus et al., 2024). When teachers are exposed to excessive workload and continuous pressure, their instructional effectiveness and classroom engagement may be negatively affected (Algar et al., 2025).

Previous studies have shown that work-related stress is associated with teaching performance. Teachers who experience higher levels of stress tend to demonstrate lower classroom effectiveness and reduced instructional quality (Bottiani et al., 2019). Stress may also influence classroom interactions and student engagement, making it more difficult for teachers to sustain high performance (Nwoko et al., 2023). Moreover, prolonged stress is often linked to burnout, which is influenced by workload and organizational conditions (Agyapong et al., 2022). In elementary education, where consistency and emotional stability are important, high levels of stress may affect both teaching effectiveness and learners' academic outcomes (Madigan et al., 2023).

Although many studies have examined work-related stress and teaching performance, limited research has focused specifically on elementary school teachers in Sirawai District, Schools Division of Zamboanga del Norte. Most existing studies have been conducted in urban schools or broader educational contexts, which may not fully reflect the experiences of teachers in geographically isolated and resource-limited areas. Thus, there is still a need for localized evidence on how work-related stress is related to teaching performance in this specific setting. This research gap emphasizes the importance of conducting a contextualized study that will provide a clearer understanding of the challenges faced by elementary school teachers in Sirawai District. Therefore, this study aims to determine the relationship between work-related stress and teaching performance among elementary school teachers in Sirawai District, Schools Division of Zamboanga del Norte. The results of the study may serve as a basis for developing an intervention program that promotes teachers' well-being and strengthens instructional effectiveness.

LITERATURE

Work-Related stress

Work-related stress among teachers is widely recognized as a major occupational concern because teaching requires sustained cognitive, emotional, and organizational effort while managing competing demands and limited resources. Jennings (2015) explained that teaching involves continuous emotional regulation and interpersonal engagement, making teachers particularly vulnerable to stress when job demands are high and coping resources are insufficient.

Agyapong et al. (2022) reported that the prevalence of stress and related conditions such as burnout, anxiety, and depression among teachers varies across contexts, indicating that work-related stress is influenced by workplace conditions. Similarly, Nwoko et al. (2023) emphasized that teachers' occupational wellbeing is shaped by multiple factors such as workload, leadership, workplace climate, and support, suggesting that stress is not only an individual experience but also an organizational issue that can affect teacher functioning.

Workload

Teacher workload is consistently identified in the literature as a major job demand that contributes to work-related stress, especially when teaching responsibilities are combined with administrative tasks, frequent reporting, and changing school expectations. OECD (2023) noted that stress is often associated with "too many lessons" and shifting requirements, indicating that heavy workload can affect teachers' job satisfaction and overall functioning in the profession. Wahab et al. (2024) found that teachers' workload increases due to administrative duties, lesson preparation, and extended working hours, and that excessive workload is associated with higher levels of stress, exhaustion, and reduced coping capacity. This suggests that when workload is not manageable, it can negatively affect teachers' wellbeing and may also influence their effectiveness in performing teaching responsibilities.

Assessments and Evaluation

Teacher stress related to assessments and evaluation is often explained through accountability pressures and the added workload associated with testing, grading, reporting, and performance monitoring. von der Embse et al. (2016) found that stronger test-based accountability pressure is associated with higher levels of teacher stress, particularly stress related to testing demands. This suggests that assessment requirements can significantly increase teachers' perceived workload and emotional strain. Jerrim and Sims (2021), using evidence from OECD TALIS, reported that school accountability systems that rely heavily on student assessment data contribute to teacher stress by increasing administrative tasks, marking load, and time pressure. They also noted that such systems may reduce teachers' sense of control over their work, which can further intensify stress and potentially affect how effectively teachers perform their duties.

Time Management

Teacher time management is often described in the literature as the perception that available time is insufficient relative to work demands, making it a significant source of work-related stress in the teaching profession. OECD (2023) reported that stressors such as having too many lessons and changing requirements are commonly associated with lower teacher job satisfaction, indicating that workload pressure and competing deadlines increase time-management strain in schools. Maas et al. (2021) found in a longitudinal study of Swiss primary and secondary teachers that higher perceived time pressure is associated with greater emotional exhaustion. This suggests that persistent time constraints and limited recovery periods can negatively affect teachers' wellbeing and may reduce their effectiveness in performing teaching responsibilities.

Classroom Behavior

Classroom behavior, particularly disruptive, aggressive, or noncompliant learner actions, is repeatedly identified as a major source of teacher work-related stress because it interrupts instruction, increases the need for constant monitoring, and heightens emotional demands in

maintaining a conducive learning environment. Aldrup et al. (2018) reported that student misbehavior is significantly associated with reduced teacher occupational wellbeing, and they highlighted that strained teacher–student relationships help explain how persistent misbehavior contributes to stress and diminished wellbeing.

Resources

Limited resources, such as inadequate instructional materials, insufficient facilities, limited ICT tools, and shortages in school-based support, are frequently identified as key work conditions that contribute to teacher work-related stress because they make it more difficult to meet instructional goals and respond to learners' needs. OECD (2023) reported that stressors vary across contexts and highlighted that working conditions, including constraints that affect teachers' ability to deliver instruction, are associated with job satisfaction and intentions to remain in the profession. This suggests that resource limitations can contribute to increased stress and lower morale among teachers.

Role of Ambiguity

Role ambiguity, defined as unclear, inconsistent, or shifting expectations about teachers' priorities and responsibilities, is a well-documented job stressor because it increases uncertainty, decision fatigue, and emotional strain in day-to-day school work. Pretorius et al. (2022) found that higher role ambiguity and role conflict are significantly associated with key burnout dimensions, such as emotional exhaustion and depersonalization, as well as lower teaching satisfaction. This suggests that unclear role expectations can increase stress and negatively affect teachers' overall functioning in the workplace. Sun et al. (2024) identified role ambiguity as a measurable factor in teachers' occupational stress and emphasized that it, along with other organizational stressors, contributes to adverse outcomes such as burnout and reduced professional functioning. This indicates that when teachers are uncertain about their roles, their ability to perform effectively may also be affected.

Emotional Demand

Teachers' emotional demands, often described as emotional labor, refer to the regulation and management of emotions to meet professional expectations in teaching. This is widely identified as a major source of work-related stress because it requires sustained patience, empathy, and self-control when dealing with learners, parents, and classroom challenges. Emotional regulation is considered an essential part of teaching, as educators are expected to maintain professionalism even under stressful conditions. Hawkins (2023) emphasized that mindfulness and self-awareness practices can help teachers manage emotional demands by improving their ability to respond calmly and effectively to challenging situations.

Support

Teacher support, particularly from school leaders, colleagues, and the broader school system, is consistently identified as an important organizational resource that influences teachers' ability to manage work-related stress. In this study, support is understood as the perceived availability of assistance, guidance, and encouragement from administrators, peers, and institutional structures in carrying out teaching responsibilities. Maas et al. (2021) found that received social support from school principals is associated with lower perceived time pressure and reduced emotional exhaustion, suggesting that supportive leadership plays a critical role in reducing stress experienced by teachers in demanding school environments. This highlights the importance of administrative support in helping teachers manage workload pressures and emotional demands.

Work-Life Balance

Work–life balance in teaching is often examined through work–family conflict, which occurs when work responsibilities consume time and energy that would otherwise be available for family and personal life, leading to increased strain and reduced recovery. Maintaining balance is important because prolonged imbalance can result in burnout and reduced effectiveness in both professional and personal domains. Valtierra (2024) emphasized the importance of structured self-care, resilience, and coping strategies in helping teachers manage professional and personal demands, particularly during the early and more challenging stages of their careers.

Teacher performance

Teacher performance in Philippine public schools is commonly measured through the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF), which translates performance targets and supporting evidence into an overall rating used for feedback, recognition, and professional development planning. The IPCRF serves as a structured evaluation tool that consolidates teachers' accomplishments and classroom-related outputs into key result areas, making it a practical basis for determining performance across the school year. Cadag (2024) emphasized that when the IPCRF is implemented as a developmental appraisal rather than a compliance requirement, it becomes more effective in improving instruction by clarifying expectations and strengthening accountability for results. This highlights its role not only as an evaluation tool but also as a mechanism for professional growth.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of the study is presented in Figure 1. Part I shows the independent variable of the study, which is work-related stress. This variable is measured using nine indicators: workload, assessment and evaluation, time management, classroom behavior, availability of resources, role ambiguity, emotional demands, support, and work–life balance. These indicators reflect the common sources of stress encountered by elementary school teachers in their daily work. A total of forty-five (45) items were used to determine the level of work-related stress experienced by the respondents. Part II presents the dependent variable, which is teaching performance. Teaching performance is measured based on the teachers' Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF), which serves as the official basis for evaluating teachers' performance in the public school system.

This framework illustrates how the different aspects of work-related stress may influence the teaching performance of elementary school teachers. It also serves as the basis for developing an appropriate intervention program aimed at helping teachers manage stress and improve their classroom performance.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to determine the work-related stress and teaching performance of the elementary school teachers of Sirawai District, Schools Division of Zamboanga Del Norte, during the school year 2025-2026.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the respondents' perceived level of work-related stress in terms of:
 - 1.1 workload;
 - 1.2 assessments and evaluation;
 - 1.3 time management;
 - 1.4 classroom behavior;
 - 1.5 resources;
 - 1.6 role of ambiguity;
 - 1.7 emotional demand;
 - 1.8 support; and
 - 1.9 work-life balance?
2. What is the respondents' level of teaching performance based on their IPCRF?
3. Is there a significant relationship between work-related stress and teaching performance?

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant relationship between work-related stress and teaching performance.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

This study focuses on the level of work-related stress and teaching performance based on the IPCRF, as well as the relationship between these two variables among 146 teacher-respondents in Sirawai District, Schools Division of Zamboanga del Norte, during School Year 2025-2026. This study is limited to two major variables: work-related stress and teaching performance. Work-related stress is measured through nine indicators, namely workload, assessment and evaluation, time management, classroom behavior, resources, role ambiguity, emotional demands, support, and work-life balance. Teaching performance, on the other hand, is based on the teachers' Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF)

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Method Used

This study used survey and descriptive-correlational methods. The survey method was used to collect data from elementary teachers in Sirawai District regarding their work-related stress and teaching performance. A questionnaire with forty-five items was used to measure work-related stress, while teaching performance was based on the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF). The survey allowed the researcher to gather information directly from the teachers about their experiences and performance. The descriptive-correlational method was used to describe the levels of work-related stress and teaching performance and to examine the relationship between these two variables. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data, while correlational analysis was used to determine whether work-related stress is associated with teaching performance. This approach measures the relationship between variables without manipulating or influencing the respondents' conditions.

Research Instrument

The questionnaire used in the study consisted of two parts. Part I measured work-related stress. The instrument was adapted from Gonzales (2024) and consisted of nine indicators, namely workload, assessment and evaluation, time management, classroom behavior, availability of resources, role ambiguity, emotional demands, support, and work-life balance. Part II assessed teacher performance based on the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF), which is aligned with the Department of Education's performance management system.

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Specifically, it was anchored on the guidelines under DepEd Order No. 2, s. 2015, and the updated guidelines under Division Memorandum No. 089, s. 2025, titled *Guidelines on the Multi-Year Performance Management and Evaluation System for Teachers for School Years 2025–2026 to 2027–2028*.

Ethical Consideration

This study secured approval from the Department of Education Research and Ethics Committee before the conduct of data gathering. Informed consent was obtained from both the institution and the individual respondents before their participation. The questionnaire was written in simple and understandable language to ensure that respondents participated voluntarily and with full awareness of the study. The identities of the respondents were kept anonymous, and all information collected was handled with strict confidentiality. Only necessary research data were kept for academic purposes and possible use in future studies.

Statistical Treatment of the Data

Presented below are the statistical tools utilized in the treatment and analysis of the data gathered.

Weighted Mean. This is used to quantify the respondents’ ratings on the work-related stress and teaching performance based on IPCRF.

Scoring Procedure

Work-Related Stress

Range of Values	Description	Interpretation
4.21-5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree	High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat Agree	Average
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low
1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Teaching Performance based on IPCRF DepEd Order No. 2, s. 2015

Scale	Range Value	Description
5	4.500–5.000	Outstanding
4	3.500–4.499	Very Satisfactory
3	2.500–3.499	Satisfactory
2	1.500–2.499	Unsatisfactory
1	below 1.499	Poor

Standard Deviation. This is used to determine the homogeneity and heterogeneity of the employee's score, where $SD \leq 3$ is homogenous and $SD > 3$ is heterogeneous Aiken & Susane (2001); Refugio, et al. (2019).

Spearman Rank-Order Correlation Coefficient (Spearman rho). This is used to determine the correlation between work-related stress and teaching performance based on IPCRF. The following guide in interpreting the correlation value proposed by Cohen, et al. (2014) was utilized in this study:

Value	Size	Interpretation
± 0.50 to ± 1.00	Large	High positive/negative correlation
± 0.30 to $\pm .49$	Medium	Moderate positive/negative correlation
± 0.10 to ± 0.29	Small	Low positive/negative correlation
± 0.01 to ± 0.09	Negligible	Slight positive/negative correlation
	0.0	No correlation

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

The data are presented following the statement of the problems of the current study. The study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the respondents’ perceived level of work-related stress in terms of:
 - 1.1 workload;
 - 1.2 assessments and evaluation;
 - 1.3 time management;
 - 1.4 classroom behavior;
 - 1.5 resources;
 - 1.6 role of ambiguity;
 - 1.7 emotional demand;
 - 1.8 support; and
 - 1.9 work-life balance?

Table 1: Teachers’ Perceived Level of Work-related Stress in Terms of the Workload

Descriptors	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. I usually feel stressed at work.	4.01	0.310	Very Stressful	High
2. I feel physically exhausted at the end of every workday.	3.27	0.748	Moderately Stressful	Moderate
3. I usually feel tense with the number of duties I’m required to do daily.	3.29	0.781	Moderately Stressful	Moderate
4. I feel stressed about combining teaching duties with non-teaching duties.	3.10	0.881	Moderately Stressful	Moderate
5. I feel a lot of pressure from my workload.	3.30	0.957	Moderately Stressful	Moderate
Overall	3.22	0.384	Moderately Stressful	Moderate

AWV-Average Weighted Value, SD-Standard Deviation

Table 1 presents the teachers’ perceived level of work-related stress in terms of workload. The overall mean of 3.22 (SD = 0.384) indicates a moderately stressful level, suggesting that workload is a consistent but manageable source of stress among the respondents. Among the indicators, “*I usually feel stressed at work*” recorded the highest mean of 4.01, interpreted as very stressful. This is followed by “*I feel a lot of pressure from my workload*” with a mean of 3.30, and “*I usually feel tense with the number of duties I’m required to do daily*” with a mean of 3.29, all interpreted as moderately stressful. Meanwhile, “*I feel stressed about combining teaching duties with non-teaching duties*” obtained the lowest mean of 3.10, also interpreted as moderately stressful.

The results indicate that teachers experience a moderate level of stress related to workload, suggesting that while work demands are present, they are still within a manageable level for most respondents. The highest rating for general work-related stress implies that accumulated responsibilities and daily demands contribute significantly to teachers’ stress experiences. This reflects how workload, when combined with multiple duties, can create a sense of pressure even if individual tasks are still manageable. However, the presence of only moderate ratings for most indicators suggests that teachers are still able to cope with their workload to a certain extent. Despite this, the consistent presence of stress indicates that workload remains a continuing concern that may affect well-being and job performance if not properly addressed.

This finding is supported by Wahab et al. (2024), who reported that administrative tasks, lesson preparation, and extended working hours contribute significantly to teachers’ workload and stress levels. Similarly, the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2023) emphasized that excessive workload and multiple job responsibilities are among the primary sources of teacher stress, which can negatively affect job satisfaction and teaching performance.

Table 2: Teachers’ Perceived Level of Work-Related Stress in Terms of the Assessment and Evaluation

Descriptors	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. I am unable to keep up with correcting papers and other schoolwork	3.12	0.953	Moderately Stressful	Moderate
2. I often find myself questioning if I’m accurately assessing students’ true understanding of the material or if I’m just assessing their test-taking skills	2.85	1.033	Moderately Stressful	Moderate
3. I worry about the weight that grades carry in determining a student’s success, both in my class and in their future endeavors	3.28	1.055	Moderately Stressful	Moderate
4. I worry about how standardized testing impacts my students’ learning experience and the pressure it puts on them	3.27	0.999	Moderately Stressful	Moderate
5. I worry about the potential for cheating or academic dishonesty during assessments, and it’s a constant battle to prevent it."	3.38	0.880	Moderately Stressful	Moderate
Overall	3.25	0.434	Moderately Stressful	Moderate

AWV-Average Weighted Value, SD-Standard Deviation

Table 2 presents the teachers’ perceived level of work-related stress in terms of assessment and evaluation. The overall mean of 3.25 (SD = 0.434) indicates a moderately stressful level. Among the indicators, concerns about the potential for cheating or academic dishonesty during assessments obtained the highest mean of 3.38, followed by “*I worry about the weight that grades carry in determining a student’s success*” with a mean of 3.28, and “*I worry about how standardized testing impacts my students’ learning experience*” with a mean of 3.27. On the other hand, “*I often find myself questioning if I’m accurately assessing students’ true understanding*” recorded the lowest mean of 2.85. All indicators are interpreted as moderately stressful.

These findings indicate that teachers experience a moderate level of stress related to assessment and evaluation, particularly in maintaining fairness, accuracy, and integrity in the assessment process. The results suggest that while teachers are able to manage these responsibilities, they still encounter concerns regarding grading, student performance evaluation, and the pressure associated with ensuring reliable assessment outcomes. The relatively higher stress associated with academic dishonesty and grading concerns reflects the critical role of teachers in safeguarding academic integrity and ensuring that assessments truly reflect student learning. Meanwhile, the moderate ratings across all indicators suggest that these stressors are persistent but not overwhelming, although they may still contribute to cumulative stress over time.

This finding is supported by Agyapong et al. (2022), who emphasized that teachers commonly experience stress related to workload demands, including grading and assessment responsibilities. Similarly, von der Embse et al. (2016) noted that accountability measures and standardized testing contribute significantly to teacher stress, as these increase pressure on teachers to ensure accurate and fair evaluation. Furthermore, Zhao et al. (2022) found that assessment-related pressures are associated with emotional strain among educators, particularly when dealing with concerns about fairness, accuracy, and student outcomes. These studies reinforce the present findings by highlighting that assessment and evaluation are significant contributors to teachers’ work-related stress across different contexts.

Table 3: Teachers’ Perceived Level of Work-related Stress in Terms of Time Management

Descriptors	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Balancing lesson planning, grading, meetings, and administrative tasks can be overwhelming.	3.46	1.018	Very Stressful	High
2. The demands of paperwork and documentation take up a significant portion of my time, leaving less for teaching and interacting with students.	3.51	0.941	Very Stressful	High
3. I often sacrifice personal time and hobbies to keep up with the demands of teaching, which can lead to burnout.	3.55	0.847	Very Stressful	High
4. I often find myself working late into the evenings or spending weekends catching up on tasks	3.53	0.963	Very Stressful	High
5. Meeting deadlines for report cards, progress reports, and other administrative tasks can be extremely stressful, especially when they all pile up at once.	3.55	0.962	Very Stressful	High
Overall	3.57	0.395	Very Stressful	High

AWV-Average Weighted Value, SD-Standard Deviation

Table 3 presents the teachers’ perceived level of work-related stress in terms of time management. The overall mean of 3.57 (SD = 0.395) indicates a very stressful level, suggesting that time-related demands are a significant source of pressure among the respondents. All indicators were interpreted as very stressful, with closely clustered mean scores ranging from 3.46 to 3.55, indicating consistency in responses. The highest mean scores of 3.55 were obtained by two indicators: “*I often sacrifice personal time and hobbies to keep up with the demands of teaching*” and “*Meeting deadlines for report cards, progress reports, and other administrative tasks can be extremely stressful.*” Meanwhile, the lowest mean of 3.46 was recorded for “*Balancing lesson planning, grading, meetings, and administrative tasks,*” although it is still interpreted as very stressful.

These findings indicate that teachers experience a high level of stress related to time management, particularly due to competing demands such as lesson preparation, administrative tasks, and strict deadlines. The results suggest that teachers frequently extend their working hours beyond the regular schedule, which affects their ability to maintain a healthy work-life balance. The consistently high ratings across all indicators imply that time-related pressures are not isolated to specific tasks but are a pervasive concern in the teaching profession. This may contribute to fatigue, reduced recovery time, and potential burnout if such demands persist over time.

This finding is supported by Maas et al. (2021), who emphasized that perceived time pressure is strongly associated with emotional exhaustion among teachers. Similarly, Wahab et al. (2024) found that workload and administrative demands significantly reduce teachers’ well-being by increasing time-related stress. In addition, Agyapong et al. (2022) highlighted that excessive workload and time constraints are major contributors

to occupational stress among educators. These studies reinforce the present findings, indicating that time management remains a critical factor influencing teachers' stress levels across different educational contexts.

Table 4: Teachers' Perceived Level of Work-Related Stress in Terms of Classroom Behavior

Descriptors	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Maintaining a positive classroom environment while addressing disruptive behavior can be a constant struggle.	3.71	0.954	Very Stressful	High
2. Dealing with challenging student behaviors daily can be emotionally exhausting.	3.52	0.991	Very Stressful	High
3. It's stressful when one disruptive student's behavior affects the entire class's learning experience	3.68	0.952	Very Stressful	High
4. I constantly feel the pressure to find the root causes of challenging behaviors and address them effectively.	3.58	1.002	Very Stressful	High
5. It's hard to remain patient and calm when faced with persistent behavioral issues, especially when it disrupts the learning process.	3.51	0.927	Very Stressful	High
Overall	3.58	0.422	Very Stressful	High

AWV-Average Weighted Value, SD-Standard Deviation

Table 4 presents the teachers' perceived level of work-related stress in terms of classroom behavior. The overall mean of 3.58 (SD = 0.422) indicates a high level of stress, suggesting that managing student behavior is a significant source of pressure among the respondents. All indicators were interpreted as very stressful, with mean scores ranging from 3.51 to 3.71, indicating consistently high levels of concern across classroom management aspects. The highest mean of 3.71 was obtained for "Maintaining a positive classroom environment while addressing disruptive behavior," followed by "It's stressful when one disruptive student's behavior affects the entire class's learning experience" with a mean of 3.68. Meanwhile, the lowest mean of 3.51 was recorded for "It's hard to remain patient and calm when faced with persistent behavioral issues," although it is still interpreted as very stressful. These findings indicate that managing classroom behavior is a significant source of work-related stress among teachers. The high level of stress suggests that maintaining discipline, ensuring student engagement, and addressing disruptive behaviors require considerable emotional and professional effort. The results further imply that classroom disruptions do not only affect individual teachers but also influence the overall learning environment, as one student's behavior can impact the entire class. This highlights the dual responsibility of teachers in managing both instruction and behavior, which may contribute to emotional strain and reduced instructional focus.

This finding is consistent with Aldrup et al. (2018), who found that student misbehavior significantly increases emotional strain among teachers. Similarly, Wettstein et al. (2023) emphasized that persistent disruptive behavior contributes to teacher stress through heightened emotional demands and classroom management challenges. In addition, Bottiani et al. (2019) reported that behavioral demands in the classroom are strongly associated with teacher burnout and reduced instructional effectiveness, reinforcing the present findings that classroom behavior is a major source of stress in the teaching profession.

Table 5: Teachers' Perceived Level of Work-Related Stress in Terms of the Resources

Descriptors	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. I constantly worry about not having enough textbooks or learning materials for all my students	3.60	1.041	Very Stressful	High
2. Limited funding for classroom supplies means I often have to purchase materials out of my pocket.	3.75	1.130	Very Stressful	High
3. Having to choose between essential resources like textbooks or classroom repairs is a constant dilemma.	3.42	1.022	Very Stressful	High
4. Teaching without access to up-to-date technology and educational tools puts my students at a disadvantage in today's digital world...	3.51	0.970	Very Stressful	High

5. Teaching without resources puts my students at a disadvantage, hindering their ability to fully engage with and benefit from modern educational practices.	3.60	1.041	Very Stressful	High
Overall	3.60	0.459	Very Stressful	High

AWV-Average Weighted Value, SD-Standard Deviation

Table 5 presents the teachers’ perceived level of work-related stress in terms of resources. The overall mean of 3.60 (SD = 0.459) indicates a high level of stress, suggesting that insufficient teaching resources significantly contribute to teachers’ work-related stress. All indicators were interpreted as very stressful, with mean scores ranging from 3.42 to 3.75, reflecting consistently high concerns across all resource-related items. The highest mean of 3.75 was obtained for “Limited funding for classroom supplies means I often have to purchase materials out of my pocket,” indicating that personal financial burden is the most stressful aspect in this domain. On the other hand, the lowest mean of 3.42 was recorded for “Having to choose between essential resources such as textbooks or classroom repairs,” although it is still interpreted as very stressful. The results indicate that limited access to teaching resources places considerable pressure on teachers, both financially and professionally. The need to personally shoulder the cost of instructional materials suggests that teachers experience added stress beyond their teaching responsibilities. Moreover, the lack of sufficient and updated resources limits instructional delivery and may affect the quality of learning experiences provided to students. This situation reflects how resource constraints can hinder effective teaching practices and contribute to overall job strain.

This finding aligns with Wahab et al. (2024), who reported that limited institutional support and resource constraints negatively affect teacher well-being. Similarly, Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2018) emphasized that insufficient job resources are strongly associated with increased stress and decreased motivation among teachers. Furthermore, the Job Demands–Resources model by Bakker and Demerouti (2007) explains that a lack of resources intensifies job demands, leading to higher levels of strain and reduced performance, which supports the present findings.

Table 6: Teachers’ Perceived Level of Work-Related Stress in Terms of Role Ambiguity

Descriptors	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. I sometimes feel overwhelmed by conflicting expectations from parents, administrators, and policymakers.	3.73	1.046	Very Stressful	High
2. I’m not always sure how much time and focus I should allocate to curriculum development versus classroom management	3.46	0.823	Very Stressful	High
3. Sometimes, I feel like I’m juggling multiple roles, from counselor to educator, without clear guidance on how to balance them.	3.35	0.951	Very Stressful	High
4. I sometimes worry that I won’t be able to meet all the expectations placed on me, and that pressure can trigger self-doubt and eventually lead to burnout.	3.48	0.948	Very Stressful	High
5. I worry about not meeting all the expectations placed on me, which can lead to self-doubt and burnout.	3.35	0.937	Very Stressful	High
Overall	3.41	0.405	Very Stressful	High

AWV-Average Weighted Value, SD-Standard Deviation

Table 6 presents the teachers’ perceived level of work-related stress in terms of role ambiguity. The overall mean of 3.41 (SD = 0.405) indicates a high level of stress, suggesting that unclear and overlapping job expectations contribute significantly to teachers’ work-related stress. All indicators were interpreted as very stressful, with mean scores ranging from 3.35 to 3.73, reflecting consistently high levels of concern across all items. The highest mean of 3.73 was obtained for “I sometimes feel overwhelmed by conflicting expectations from parents, administrators, and policymakers,” indicating that external demands from multiple stakeholders create the greatest uncertainty. Meanwhile, the lowest means of 3.35 were recorded for “Sometimes, I feel like I’m juggling multiple roles...” and “I worry about not meeting all the expectations placed on me,” although both are still interpreted as very stressful. The results indicate that role ambiguity is a significant source of work-related stress among teachers. The presence of conflicting expectations from parents, administrators, and policymakers creates uncertainty in decision-making and performance, which increases psychological pressure. Additionally, the findings suggest that teachers are often required to assume multiple roles

without clear guidance, making it difficult to balance responsibilities effectively. This lack of clarity may lead to feelings of self-doubt and emotional strain.

This finding is consistent with the Job Demands–Resources model of Bakker and Demerouti (2007), which posits that role ambiguity functions as a job demand that increases strain and reduces well-being. Similarly, Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2018) found that unclear roles and expectations are significant contributors to teacher stress and reduced motivation. In addition, Maas et al. (2021) support these findings by highlighting that overlapping and unclear demands contribute to emotional exhaustion among teachers, reinforcing the present results on role ambiguity as a key stressor.

Table 7: Teachers’ Perceived Level of Work-Related Stress in Terms of Emotional Demands

Descriptors	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Dealing with students’ anger, frustration, and emotional outbursts can be mentally and physically exhausting.	3.43	0.946	Very Stressful	High
2. The emotional labor of teaching, especially when dealing with diverse student backgrounds and needs, can be overwhelming.	3.55	0.940	Very Stressful	High
3. I often feel like I’m carrying the emotional burden of my students, and it can be a heavy weight to bear	3.38	0.984	Moderately Stressful	Moderate
4. I worry about the long-term impact of emotional stress on my mental health.	3.32	0.924	Moderately Stressful	Moderate
5. Balancing my own emotions while helping students navigate their emotional struggles can be emotionally draining.	3.36	0.995	Moderately Stressful	Moderate
Overall	3.42	0.416	Very Stressful	High

AWV-Average Weighted Value, SD-Standard Deviation

Table 7 presents the teachers’ perceived level of work-related stress in terms of emotional demands. The overall mean of 3.42 (SD = 0.416) indicates a high level of stress, suggesting that emotional labor is a substantial source of strain among teachers. The highest mean (3.55) was recorded for “The emotional labor of teaching, especially when dealing with diverse student backgrounds and needs, can be overwhelming,” indicating that managing diverse emotional and behavioral needs places a significant burden on teachers. The lowest mean (3.32) was obtained for “I worry about the long-term impact of emotional stress on my mental health,” although it still reflects a moderate level of stress. The results show that teachers experience considerable emotional strain in managing students’ emotional needs while regulating their own responses. This highlights the emotional labor inherent in teaching, where teachers are not only expected to deliver instruction but also to provide emotional support to learners. The demands of dealing with students’ emotional outbursts, diverse needs, and personal challenges contribute to psychological fatigue. At the same time, teachers must maintain emotional composure, which adds to the overall stress. These findings suggest that emotional demands in teaching are not only frequent but also sustained, potentially affecting teachers’ well-being and their ability to perform effectively in the classroom.

This finding is supported by Kariou et al. (2021), who emphasized that emotional labor is strongly associated with teacher burnout and stress. Similarly, Sun et al. (2025) found that managing emotional demands in teaching significantly contributes to emotional exhaustion and turnover intention. In addition, Madigan et al. (2023) highlighted that sustained emotional stress in teaching is linked to negative impacts on teachers’ psychological well-being, reinforcing the present findings that emotional demands are a major source of stress among teachers.

Table 8: Teachers’ Perceived Level of Work-Related Stress in Terms of Lack of Support

Descriptors	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. I constantly worry about not having enough textbooks or learning materials for all my students.	3.51	0.970	Very Stressful	High
2. Limited funding for classroom supplies means I often have to purchase materials out of my pocket.	3.51	1.078	Very Stressful	High
3. Having to choose between essential resources like textbooks or classroom repairs is a constant dilemma.	3.38	0.949	Moderately Stressful	Moderate

4. Teaching without access to up-to-date technology and educational tools puts my students at a disadvantage in today's digital world.	3.51	0.904	Very Stressful	High
5. Teaching without resources puts my students at a disadvantage, hindering their ability to fully engage with and benefit from modern educational practices.	3.53	0.998	Very Stressful	High
Overall	3.50	0.461	Very Stressful	High

AWV-Average Weighted Value, SD-Standard Deviation

Table 8 presents the teachers' perceived level of work-related stress in terms of lack of support stress. The overall mean of 3.50 (SD = 0.461) indicates a high level of stress, suggesting that teachers perceive insufficient institutional and system-level support in performing their instructional responsibilities.

Most indicators were interpreted as very stressful, with mean scores ranging from 3.38 to 3.53. The highest mean (3.53) was obtained for "Teaching without resources puts my students at a disadvantage, hindering their ability to fully engage with and benefit from modern educational practices," indicating teachers' concern about the consequences of inadequate institutional support on instructional quality and learner engagement. Several indicators obtained the same mean (3.51), particularly those reflecting limited access to instructional materials, personal financial burden, and lack of educational tools and technology. These responses suggest that teachers perceive a gap in institutional provision and systemic assistance necessary for effective teaching. Meanwhile, the lowest mean (3.38) was recorded for "Having to choose between essential resources like textbooks or classroom repairs," although this still reflects a moderate level of stress. Overall, the results indicate that teachers experience stress when institutional systems fail to provide sufficient support structures that would otherwise facilitate effective teaching and classroom delivery.

Although the indicators are similar to the resource-related stress domain, this variable was interpreted in terms of institutional and systemic support, particularly the extent to which schools and administrators are able to provide timely assistance, funding, and instructional support to teachers. This means that the stress experienced is not only due to the absence of materials, but also reflects the perceived inadequacy of the support system responsible for providing those resources.

This finding is supported by Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2018), who emphasized that lack of job resources, including social and organizational support, is strongly associated with increased teacher stress and reduced motivation. Similarly, Bakker and Demerouti (2017), in the Job Demands–Resources framework, highlighted that insufficient support systems intensify job strain and reduce well-being. In addition, Wahab et al. (2024) found that inadequate institutional support contributes significantly to teacher burnout and reduced job satisfaction, reinforcing the present findings that lack of support is a major source of stress among teachers.

Table 9: Teachers' Perceived Level of Work-Related Stress in Terms of Work-Life Balance

Descriptors	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Finding time for my personal life and hobbies is a constant struggle when teaching demands so much of my time.	3.56	0.968	Very Stressful	High
2. I often feel like I'm taking work home with me, both physically and mentally, which makes it hard to disconnect.	3.40	0.860	Very Stressful	High
3. I sometimes must sacrifice weekends and evenings to keep up with the demands of teaching	3.37	0.895	Moderately Stressful	Moderate
4. I sometimes feel like I'm neglecting my own needs in the pursuit of providing the best education for my students.	3.46	0.933	Very Stressful	High
<i>Table 17 Continued</i>				
5. I often feel guilty when I need to take time off for my well-being or to attend to personal matters.	3.42	0.988	Very Stressful	High
Overall	3.43	0.421	Very Stressful	High

AWV-Average Weighted Value, SD-Standard Deviation

Table 9 presents the teachers' perceived level of work-related stress in terms of work-life balance. The overall mean of 3.43 (SD = 0.421) indicates a high level of stress, suggesting that difficulties in balancing professional responsibilities and personal life significantly contribute to

teachers' work-related stress. Most indicators were interpreted as very stressful, with mean scores ranging from 3.37 to 3.56. The highest mean (3.56) was obtained for "Finding time for my personal life and hobbies is a constant struggle when teaching demands so much of my time," indicating that time constraints significantly affect teachers' personal well-being. Several indicators, such as taking work home and neglecting personal needs, also obtained high mean scores, reflecting the continuous demands of the teaching profession. Meanwhile, the lowest mean (3.37) was recorded for "I sometimes must sacrifice weekends and evenings to keep up with the demands of teaching," although it still reflects a moderate level of stress, indicating that work extends beyond regular hours.

The results indicate that teachers experience difficulty maintaining a healthy balance between their professional and personal lives. The demands of teaching often extend beyond regular working hours, requiring teachers to bring work home and dedicate additional time outside of school. This situation limits opportunities for rest, leisure, and personal recovery, which are essential for maintaining well-being. As a result, teachers may experience emotional fatigue, reduced energy, and increased stress levels over time. Furthermore, feelings of guilt when attending to personal needs suggest that teachers may prioritize work over self-care, which can further contribute to long-term stress and potential burnout.

This finding is supported by Maas et al. (2021), who found that high time pressure and workload are strongly associated with emotional exhaustion among teachers. Similarly, Wahab et al. (2024) emphasized that excessive workload negatively affects teachers' well-being and work-life balance, leading to increased stress levels. In addition, Agyapong et al. (2022) highlighted that prolonged work demands reduce recovery time and contribute to occupational stress, reinforcing the present findings that work-life imbalance is a major source of stress among teachers.

Table 10: Summary of the Teachers' Perceived Level of Work-Related Stress

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
A. Workload	3.22	0.384	Moderately Stressful	Moderate
B. Assessment and Evaluation	3.25	0.434	Moderately Stressful	Moderate
C. Time Management	3.57	0.395	Very Stressful	High
D. Classroom Management	3.58	0.422	Very Stressful	High
E. Resources	3.60	0.459	Very Stressful	High
F. Role Ambiguity	3.41	0.405	Very Stressful	High
G. Emotional Demands	3.42	0.416	Very Stressful	High
H. Lack of Support	3.50	0.461	Very Stressful	High
<i>Table 18 Continued</i>				
I. Work-life Balance	3.43	0.421	Very Stressful	High
Overall	3.44	0.123	Very Stressful	High

SD-Standard Deviation

Table 10 summarizes the teachers' perceived level of work-related stress across multiple domains. The overall mean of 3.44 (SD = 0.123) indicates a high level of stress, suggesting that teachers experience considerable work-related pressure across various professional demands. Among the domains, stress related to resources (M = 3.60), classroom management (M = 3.58), and time management (M = 3.57) were the highest, indicating that inadequate materials, classroom behavior challenges, and balancing multiple tasks are major sources of stress. Role ambiguity (M = 3.41), emotional demands (M = 3.42), lack of support (M = 3.50), and work-life balance (M = 3.43) were all rated as very stressful, showing that these stressors are consistently experienced by teachers. In contrast, workload (M = 3.22) and assessment and evaluation (M = 3.25) were rated as moderately stressful, suggesting that while these areas contribute to stress, they are comparatively less intense than the other domains.

The results indicate that teachers experience high levels of stress across multiple aspects of their professional responsibilities. The high ratings in resources, classroom management, and time management suggest that teachers face challenges in managing instructional demands alongside limited materials and classroom-related concerns. The consistently high stress levels in role ambiguity, emotional demands, lack of support, and work-life balance further indicate that stress is not limited to a single factor but is instead multidimensional. This suggests that teachers are exposed to both internal and external pressures that affect their well-being. Meanwhile, workload and assessment-related tasks, while still stressful, appear to be relatively more manageable compared to other domains.

These findings align with the OECD (2023), which noted that excessive workload and administrative demands significantly contribute to teacher stress and affect job satisfaction. Similarly, Agyapong et al. (2022) highlighted that multiple job demands are strongly associated with stress and burnout among educators. Wahab et al. (2024) also emphasized that limited institutional support and heavy workload negatively impact teachers' well-being. Furthermore, the Job Demands-Resources framework of Bakker and Demerouti (2007, 2017) and the findings of Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2018) explain that the combination of high demands and insufficient resources leads to increased stress levels, which supports the results of the present study.

2. What is the respondents' level of teaching performance based on their IPCRF?

Table 11: Level of Teachers' Performance Based on IPCRF

Scale	Range Values	of	Description	F	Percent	AWV	Description
1	below 1.499		Poor	0	0.00		
2	1.500-2.499		Unsatisfactory	0	0.00		
3	2.500-3.499		Satisfactory	6	4.10	4.01	0.310
4	3.500-4.499		Very Satisfactory	132	90.40		Very Satisfactory
5	4.500-5.000		Outstanding	8	5.50		
Total				146			

F=Frequency

Table 11 presents the level of teachers' performance based on their Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) ratings. The data show that the majority of teachers (90.40%, n = 132) were rated as Very Satisfactory, while 5.50% (n = 8) achieved an Outstanding rating and 4.10% (n = 6) were rated as Satisfactory. The overall mean of 4.01 (SD = 0.310) indicates a Very Satisfactory level of performance, suggesting that teachers, on average, demonstrate a high level of competence in their professional responsibilities.

The results indicate that teachers maintain a high level of professional performance as reflected in their IPCRF ratings. The predominance of Very Satisfactory ratings suggests consistent effectiveness in instructional delivery, classroom management, lesson preparation, and other teaching-related tasks. This is notable considering the high levels of work-related stress identified in the previous tables. Despite these stressors, teachers are still able to perform their duties effectively, which may reflect their adaptability, commitment, and professional resilience. The presence of Outstanding ratings further suggests that a portion of teachers are able to exceed expectations, even under demanding work conditions.

These findings are supported by Day and Gu (2014), who explained that resilient teachers are able to sustain professional effectiveness despite ongoing job demands by drawing on internal and external resources, adaptive strategies, and strong professional commitment. Their work highlights that resilience enables teachers to maintain instructional quality and job performance even when facing multiple stressors. This supports the present findings, suggesting that factors such as experience, coping strategies, and professional commitment may help buffer the potential negative effects of stress on teaching performance.

3. Is there a significant relationship between work-related stress and teaching performance?

Table 12: Test of the Relationship Between the Teachers' Work-Related Stress and Teaching Performance Based on IPCRF

Variables		Teaching Performance based on IPCRF
Workload	Correlation Coefficient	0.049
	p-value	0.560
Assessment and Evaluation	Correlation Coefficient	-0.118
	p-value	0.157
Time Management Stress	Correlation Coefficient	0.104
	p-value	0.210
Classroom Behavior	Correlation Coefficient	0.024
	p-value	0.777
Resources	Correlation Coefficient	0.060
	p-value	0.475
Role Ambiguity Stress	Correlation Coefficient	0.013
	p-value	0.876
Emotional Demands Stress	Correlation Coefficient	-0.013
	p-value	0.880
Lack of Support Stress	Correlation Coefficient	-0.014
	p-value	0.866
Work-Life Balance Stress	Correlation Coefficient	0.167*
	p-value	0.044
Overall Work-Related Stress	Correlation Coefficient	0.108
	p-value	0.193

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level

Table 12 presents the relationship between teachers' work-related stress and teaching performance based on IPCRF (N = 146). The results show that most dimensions of work-related stress have very weak and non-significant relationships with teaching performance. These include workload (r = 0.049, p = 0.560), assessment and evaluation (r = -0.118, p = 0.157), time management stress (r = 0.104, p = 0.210), classroom behavior (r = 0.024, p = 0.777), resources (r = 0.060, p = 0.475), role ambiguity stress (r = 0.013, p = 0.876), emotional demands stress (r = -0.013, p = 0.880), and lack of support stress (r = -0.014, p = 0.866). These results indicate that these specific stress domains do not significantly relate to teachers' IPCRF performance. In contrast, work-life balance stress shows a weak but statistically significant positive relationship with

teaching performance ($r = 0.167$, $p = 0.044$), indicating that teachers who are better able to manage the demands between work and personal life tend to demonstrate slightly higher performance ratings. However, the magnitude of this relationship remains weak.

Overall, teachers' work-related stress does not have a significant relationship with teaching performance based on IPCRF ($r = 0.108$, $p = 0.193$). This indicates that, in general, variations in teachers' stress levels are not significantly associated with differences in their performance ratings. The null hypothesis is therefore accepted, suggesting that work-related stress, as a whole, does not significantly influence teaching performance in this study. The findings imply that teachers are able to maintain their level of teaching performance despite experiencing various forms of work-related stress. This may be attributed to professional resilience, coping strategies, and adherence to performance standards required in the IPCRF. While certain aspects such as work-life balance show some degree of relationship, the overall results suggest that teaching performance is influenced by other factors beyond stress alone.

This finding is supported by Day and Gu (2014), who emphasized that teachers can sustain professional effectiveness despite ongoing job demands through resilience and commitment. Similarly, Hattie (2003) highlighted that teacher expertise plays a significant role in maintaining student outcomes even under challenging conditions. The Learning Policy Institute (2017) also noted that teaching experience and professional growth contribute to sustained performance, which may help buffer the potential effects of work-related stress.

DISCUSSION

The findings of the study revealed that elementary school teachers in Sirawai District experienced a high level of work-related stress, particularly in the areas of resources, classroom management, and time management. This suggests that teachers are highly affected by the lack of adequate instructional materials, challenges in managing learner behavior, and the difficulty of balancing multiple teaching and non-teaching responsibilities. Although workload and assessment and evaluation were only rated as moderately stressful, these still contributed to the overall stress experienced by the teachers. The results indicate that work-related stress among teachers is multidimensional and is not caused by a single factor alone. Instead, it comes from the combined effects of limited resources, classroom demands, time pressure, emotional demands, lack of support, role ambiguity, and work-life imbalance. These findings support the idea that when job demands are high and available resources are limited, teachers are more likely to experience stress, as explained in the Job Demands–Resources framework.

Despite the high level of work-related stress, the teachers' performance based on the IPCRF was generally rated Very Satisfactory. This means that the teachers were still able to perform their duties effectively even when they were experiencing various stressors in their work environment. This may be attributed to their professional commitment, resilience, coping strategies, and adherence to the standards required by the Department of Education. The results further showed that overall work-related stress had no significant relationship with teaching performance, indicating that teachers' stress levels did not significantly affect their IPCRF ratings. However, work-life balance stress had a weak but significant positive relationship with teaching performance, suggesting that teachers who experienced or managed work-life balance concerns may still demonstrate slightly higher performance. This implies that teaching performance may be influenced not only by stress but also by other factors such as experience, professional competence, motivation, administrative support, and personal coping mechanisms. Therefore, while teachers in Sirawai District continue to maintain satisfactory performance, the presence of high stress levels highlights the need for intervention programs such as Project GABAY to strengthen teacher support, improve resource allocation, address role ambiguity, and promote teacher well-being.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that elementary school teachers in Sirawai District experience a high level of work-related stress, particularly in terms of resources, classroom management, time management, lack of support, work-life balance, emotional demands, and role ambiguity; however, their teaching performance based on the IPCRF remains Very Satisfactory. This means that despite the presence of various work-related stressors, teachers are still able to perform their instructional and professional responsibilities effectively. Moreover, overall work-related stress has no significant relationship with teaching performance, which indicates that stress does not significantly affect teachers' IPCRF-based performance. However, work-life balance stress has a weak but significant positive relationship with teaching performance, suggesting that teachers who manage their professional and personal responsibilities may still maintain effective performance. Thus, the findings imply that teachers demonstrate resilience, commitment, and coping ability, but intervention programs such as Project GABAY are still necessary to reduce stressors, strengthen support systems, and promote teacher well-being and instructional effectiveness.

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